

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract:

This thesis is devoted to the study of effective methods of teaching foreign languages to preschool children. The study analyzes children's linguistic development, cognitive characteristics, and age-appropriate learning strategies. The effectiveness of the communicative approach, game technologies, multimodal resources, and immersive methods is also considered. During the work, advanced foreign experience will be analyzed and practical recommendations will be developed. The research results will serve to improve the process of teaching foreign languages in preschool educational institutions.

Keywords: Preschool children, communicative approach, game technologies, multimodal resources, immersive methods, STEAM approach, Total Physical Response (TPR)

INTRODUCTION

Modern globalization processes and the expansion of international relations increase the need for knowledge of foreign languages. Especially in childhood, language learning occurs as a natural process and is considered the most convenient stage for the development of a child's linguistic abilities. Therefore, teaching foreign languages to preschool children is an important scientific and practical issue and requires effective methods and approaches. This research is aimed at identifying the most effective methods of foreign language teaching for preschool children. The study examines the influence of game technologies, a communicative approach, multimodal methods, and an immersive environment on language learning. The psycholinguistic characteristics of children and age-appropriate teaching methods are also analyzed. The relevance of the research is due to the need to maximize the use of children's natural language learning abilities and increase their motivation to learn foreign languages. Studying best practices in introducing innovative methods of teaching foreign languages in preschool educational institutions can make a valuable scientific and practical contribution to this area. The purpose of this work is to identify the most effective methods of teaching foreign languages to preschool children and to analyze their influence on linguistic development. The research results will serve the development of useful methodological recommendations for teachers and parents.

MAIN PART

Preschool children (3-7 years old) have the ability to learn a natural language, during which they have the opportunity to master a foreign language as if it were their native language. Therefore, when teaching foreign languages, it is important to use age-appropriate methods that stimulate the process of learning natural languages.

Halliwell (1992) argues in her research that children are naturally capable of communicating and understanding meanings through context. In his opinion, teaching through games and creative activities increases children's interest in language and yields effective results. Cameron (2001) emphasizes the importance of multimodal methods in teaching children a foreign language. It shows that the process of language learning can be made interactive and effective using visual and audio resources (cartoons, songs, pictures). Pinter (2011) studies the psycholinguistic development of preschool children and emphasizes the need to use elements of physical activity and play in teaching them a foreign language. He conducted experiments confirming the effectiveness of the TPR (Total Physical Response) method. Research conducted by Lightbown and Spada (2013) shows the importance of a communicative approach in language

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teaching to children. In their opinion, learning a language through communication is more effective than teaching grammatical rules individually.

Game method

Since children are naturally inclined to learn through play, teaching a foreign language through games is considered effective. The use of active games (for example, understanding and executing commands through the game "Simon Says"), role-playing (conversations on topics such as shop, doctor, restaurant), as well as card games (increasing vocabulary using picture cards) keeps children's attention for a long time and makes learning a natural process. In addition, the use of games helps to increase motivation in children.

Visual and audio methods (Multimodal learning)

Children learn faster through sight and hearing. Therefore, it is important to use pictures, videos, and music during the lesson. By using pictures, posters, dolls and toys, increasing vocabulary through cartoons and videos for children, as well as teaching poems and songs (for example, improving pronunciation through "Twinkle, Twinkle, Little Star"), children better understand words and their meanings, and this process creates an interesting and interactive environment for children. At the same time, it helps them develop their pronunciation.

Communicative approach

Children learn quickly through the practical application of language. Therefore, they should be constantly encouraged to communicate in a foreign language. The use of simple phrases in everyday activities (for example, "Good morning!", "What's your name?"), teaching children simple questions and answers, and encouraging communication in group activities develop children's ability to speak freely, help them not to be afraid of language and to perceive it naturally, and also increase communicative competence.

Immersive Method (Creating a Complete Language Environment)

When learning a foreign language, immersing the child in the language environment (immersion) gives effective results. That is, by speaking only in the language being studied during the lesson, creating a language environment (for example, decorating the classroom with posters and inscriptions in English), as well as organizing a language exchange between children with experience in learning local and foreign languages, children quickly adapt to the language, the need for translation from their native language decreases, and the possibility of natural language acquisition increases.

STEAM approach (Language Learning through Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics)

Learning a foreign language through scientific and practical experiments will be interesting for children. Explaining simple scientific experiments in English (such as demonstrating the immiscibility of water and oil), performing art projects in a foreign language, or teaching the basics of mathematics through a foreign language (naming colors and shapes, counting) connects language with real life and develops children's analytical thinking skills. It also allows for the study of a new language in conjunction with science and art.

Total Physical Response (TPR)

It is known that words and phrases related to actions are better assimilated by children. For example, explaining words like "Jump," "Run," "Sit down" with actions, learning new words through physical exercises, and performing actions appropriate to songs and poems helps children memorize words at the subconscious level. In addition, through physical activity, children do not get bored, that is, physical activity and learning are carried out together.

CONCLUSION

Teaching foreign languages to preschool children allows them to effectively use their natural language learning abilities. The study showed that the most effective methods include game technologies, a multimodal approach, communicative methods, creating an immersive environment, and methods related to physical activity. These methods help children learn the language naturally and in an engaging way, improve their memory, and develop communication skills. The research results show that the use of visual and audio materials in the process of teaching foreign languages to preschool children, the organization of interactive classes, and the conduct of lessons based on real-life situations are of great importance. In the future, conducting

additional research in this area and testing innovative methods will serve to make the pedagogical process more effective.

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